

Conceptual Design of a Novel Variable Stiffness Actuator for Shoulder Joint Applications

Sandhya Chandrasekaran*, Giorgio Grioli*[†], Manuel Giuseppe Catalano*, and Antonio Bicchi*[†]

*Soft Robotics for Human Cooperation and Rehabilitation

Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, Genova, Italy

[†]Department of Information Engineering and Research Centre “E. Piaggio”

University of Pisa, Pisa, Italy

Email: {sandhya.chandrasekaran, giorgio.grioli, manuel.catalano, antonio.bicchi}@iit.it

Abstract—The aim of this paper is to develop a Variable Stiffness Actuator (VSA), based on the agonistic-antagonistic working principle. The actuator is designed for use in the shoulder of a humanoid service robot, AlterEgo and hence is designed to have the flexion-extension range of motion of a human shoulder.

Index Terms—Variable Stiffness Actuator, bi-directional, agonist-antagonist, shoulder joint.

I. INTRODUCTION

Robotics is rapidly advancing towards integration into daily human life. With the increase in human-robot interaction and cooperation, it is essential to consider the presence of external forces that could potentially cause harm to either the user or the robot itself. As a result, there has been significant progress over the years in the development of Variable Stiffness Actuators (VSAs).

A VSA is an actuator that is capable of deviation when an external force is applied [1]. The presence of a compliant element enables the actuator to be able to adapt to external perturbations while the ability to change the compliance gives the user a control over the level of influence the environment has on the actuator. VSAs consist of an actuation system for the motion and a stiffness control system, and are generally categorised based on the method of stiffness variation [2].

VSAs have a wide range of applications and including use in humanoid robots and prosthesis. One notable example is the humanoid robot AlterEgo [3], built for the Avatar XPRIZE competition (2022) [4], has a fully functional anthropomorphic upper body that is actuated using the VSACube [5]. The VSACube is built using a bi-directional antagonistic setup in which the two motors operate in coordination for actuation and stiffness control. The shoulder of AlterEgo is a DC motor unit (as seen in Figure 1).

This paper aims to develop a variable stiffness actuator (VSA) designed for the shoulder joint of the AlterEgo system. The actuator’s performance is intended to match and improve the current capabilities of AlterEgo’s shoulder. The VSA operates based on an agonist-antagonist mechanism for stiffness variation, as described in the following sections.

Fig. 1: AlterEgo humanoid robot with the current shoulder motor setup

II. MODEL DESCRIPTION

In this section, the mathematical model developed for the Variable Stiffness Actuator (VSA) designed for the shoulder joint of the AlterEgo humanoid robot is presented.

The stiffness of the actuator is varied by changing the active length of the springs. Motion of the motors in the same direction moves the output shaft (helping mode) and the torques of the two motors add up. When the motors move in opposite directions the stiffness is varied (Normal mode) and there is no net effective output torque. [6]

The design of the current system is developed based on the Half-Linear (HL) configuration proposed in [7]. The each side of the design consists of a a linear and a non-linear system on either side. The non-linear system consists of a floating spring between either side, integrating the cross-coupled and bidirectional arrangement in antagonistic VSAs [1]. The pulleys are also connected to the motors via worm

gears to achieve a non back drivable system.

Fig. 2: Force Distribution in the System

Based on the assumption that the length of the tendons is fixed, the total length of the tendons for the linear and non linear sides can be expressed as a function of the rotation of the motors θ_i ($i = 1, 2$) and the rotation of the output shaft q .

$$L_{T,nl} = r(2\pi + (\theta - q)) + L_1 + L_2 \quad (1)$$

where, L_1 and L_2 are functions of θ and q and r is the radius of the pulleys.

The elongation of the floating non-linear spring can be calculated from the following set of equations.

$$p = L_1 \cos \beta_{\theta,i} + L_2 \cos \beta_q \quad (2)$$

$$H_t = L_1 \sin \gamma - \beta_{\theta,i} + L_2 \sin \gamma + \beta_q \quad (3)$$

$$2b = L_{\theta,1} \cos(\gamma - \beta_{\theta,1}) + x_{nl} + \Delta x_{nl} \quad (4)$$

$$+ L_{\theta,2} \cos(\gamma - \beta_{\theta,2}) + 2r \sin \gamma$$

where, $\beta_{\theta,i} = f(\theta_i, q)$ and γ is the constructional value of base angle in the triangular arrangement of the pulleys.

Similarly, the elongation of the linear springs is calculated from the following set of equations [7]

$$L_{T,l} = L_3 + L_4 + r(2\pi + (q - \theta_i)) + 2\pi r_p + 2L_{h,i} \quad (5)$$

$$L_{h,i} = h_l - (r + r_p + x_l + \Delta x_l) \quad (6)$$

The forces on the output pulley by the tendons can be hence expressed in terms of β_q , $\beta_{\theta,i}$ and the extension of the linear and non-linear springs. The forces on the non-linear sides can be expressed as

$$F_{q,i} = -\frac{1}{\cos \beta_q + \sin \beta_q} \left(\frac{\tau_\theta}{r} (\cos \beta_\theta + \sin \beta_\theta) \right. \quad (7)$$

$$\left. + k_{nl} \Delta x_{nl} (\cos(\gamma) + \sin(\gamma)) \right) - \frac{\tau_{ext}}{r}$$

where $i = 1, 2$ and k_{nl} is the stiffness of the non-linear spring.

Similarly, the forces on the pulley by the linear half can be expressed as

$$F_{q,i} = -\left(\frac{\tau_\theta}{r} + k_l \Delta x_l - \frac{\tau_{ext}}{r} \right) \quad (8)$$

where $i = 3, 4$ and k_l is the stiffness of the linear springs.

The torques on the system would be

$$\tau_{left} = r(F_{q,1} - F_{q,4}) \quad (9)$$

$$\tau_{right} = r(F_{q,2} - F_{q,3}) \quad (10)$$

$$\tau_{op} = \tau_{left} + \tau_{right} \quad (11)$$

The stiffness of the output shaft can be calculated from the calculated torques as the derivative with respect to the the position, q [7].

$$\sigma(q, \theta_1, \theta_2) = \frac{\partial \tau(q, \theta_1, \theta_2)}{\partial q} \quad (12)$$

$$= \frac{\partial \tau_{left}(q, \theta_1)}{\partial q} + \frac{\partial \tau_{right}(q, \theta_2)}{\partial q}$$

$$= \sigma_{left} + \sigma_{right}$$

Hence, (12) gives the expression of the stiffness of the output shaft in terms of the inputs of the system (θ_1, θ_2, q). Since the stiffness of the output shaft is dependant on the spring extension, the accurate model for stiffness can be estimated through practical experimentation, by fitting the observed values to a curve.

III. INFERENCE AND FUTURE WORK

This paper introduced a conceptual design for a variable stiffness actuator optimized for shoulder motion in humanoid robots. Through theoretical analysis and performance calculations, the design demonstrates significant potential in terms of compliance and the mathematical results provide confidence in the feasibility of the proposed system.

Future work will involve prototyping, experimental validation, and further refinement to ensure practical implementation. The stiffness model would be determined based on experimental values and curve fitting. This study marks a promising step toward developing more adaptable and flexible robotic actuators for human-robot interaction.

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